

1 **Effects of spatial autocorrelation structure for friction angle on the**
2 **runout distance in heterogeneous sand collapse**

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4 **Abstract**

5 This paper proposes a stochastic method for analyzing the runout distance of sand collapse
6 considering the spatial variability of shear strength, in which random field theory and generalized
7 interpolation material point method are integrated into a Monte-Carlo simulation basis. The
8 random field is generated by Cholesky matrix decomposition method and implemented into the
9 material point level, hence heterogeneity and large deformations are simultaneously considered in
10 the modeling process. A sand collapse case is simulated with both homogeneous and
11 heterogeneous condition assumptions by the proposed method. The effect of five theoretical
12 autocorrelation functions (ACFs) on the runout distance of the collapse is highlighted since the
13 ACFs are commonly adopted to characterize the spatial variability of soil properties due to sparse
14 site observation data. It is shown that the deterministic analysis may underestimate the runout
15 distance, while the heterogeneous model provides realistic results. Moreover, five ACFs and

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16 different coefficients of variation of friction angle (COV_{φ}) are compared to investigate their
17 influences on the runout distance modeling. The results show that the uncertainty of runout
18 distance increases with the increase in COV_{φ} . Meanwhile, the variances of the runout distance
19 also become larger with COV_{φ} increasing. Based on the proportion of the runout distance which
20 exceeds the deterministic value, the results indicate that the deterministic analysis notably
21 underestimates the risk induced by large runout distances in real heterogeneous granular flows
22 (e.g., landslide, debris-avalanches).

23 **Author Keywords:** Random field, Sand collapse, Runout distance, Spatial variability.

24 1. Introduction

25 In nature, the flow of granular material is a common phenomenon in geological disasters such as
26 landslides, debris flows, and avalanches (Crosta et al., 2009; Ma et al., 2018). Therefore, landslides
27 are often treated as granular flows with diverse behaviors ranging from solid-like to fluid-like.
28 Landslides as a real geophysical flow are primarily driven by gravity and could result in
29 catastrophic damages along their extensive motion paths, such as destroying transportation
30 infrastructures, facilities, and buildings (Huang and Fan, 2013). Especially, all transportation in
31 mountainous regions face great challenges given their exposure to long runout distance and huge
32 influence zone of potential landslides (Yerro et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2020). Additionally, this is
33 further complicated due to the spatial variability of the geomaterials involved, with natural
34 heterogeneity in these flows. Therefore, for risk assessment and disaster mitigation, prediction of
35 the final extent of granular flow in spatially varying deposits is crucial to precisely investigate the
36 post-failure behavior, which plays a significant role in real landslides.

37 Collapse of a granular column has been extensively studied in the case of dry granular material
38 (Fern and Soga, 2017). Lube et al. (2004) and Lajeunesse et al. (2004) are the first to conduct the
39 experiments by releasing a column of granular material on a flat surface to investigate the flow
40 mechanisms and geometrical properties of the final deposits. Since then, granular flows are also
41 investigated using several numerical approaches such as discrete element method (DEM) (Guo
42 and Curtis, 2015), smooth particle hydrodynamics (SPH) (Bui et al., 2008; Nguyen et al., 2017),
43 and material point method (MPM) (Li et al., 2018) which compensated the details of granular
44 flows on stress-strain and final runout distance by different aspect ratios and mechanical parameter
45 settings. Among the mentioned methods, DEM is deemed to be an accurate approach to simulate
46 granular flows, but it requires demanding computational resources for a practical problem
47 involving hundreds of millions of particles. In addition, the difficulty in selection of appropriate
48 micro-parameters is a main drawback in DEM, particularly for practical level simulations
49 (Benvenuti et al., 2016). As for particle-based method, inconsistent near boundaries (Morris, 1996)
50 and tensile instability (Bui et al., 2008) would result in low accuracy and greatly limit the
51 application of SPH in geo-engineering. This leads to the increasing development and application
52 of MPM in modeling granular flow problems (Bardenhagen et al., 2000; Iaconeta et al., 2017; Li
53 et al., 2018). However, in previous studies the granular materials are always assumed to be
54 homogeneous and modeled with simplified homogeneous and isotropic material models without
55 considering the spatial variability and uncertainty of their heterogeneity. Meanwhile, it is
56 impractical to conduct hundreds of physical experiments to investigate the runout distance affected
57 by natural heterogeneities in different geomaterial deposits. However, in engineering geology,
58 variability of natural geomaterials (e.g., sand, silt, clay) is extensively admitted, and it is agreed
59 that the spatial distributions of shear strength parameters (e.g., internal friction angle φ and

60 cohesion c) notably influence the likelihood and failure mode of these flows, thereby influencing
61 their post-failure behavior and runout motion. Kerswell (2005) indicated that the runout behavior
62 of granular flows has a clear material dependence, even little variability in material strength could
63 result in a totally different response. According to Crosta et al. (2009) and Zhang and Xiao (2019)
64 the internal friction angle plays a particularly important role on the post-failure behavior of
65 granular flows. However, currently conventional deterministic particle-based methods cannot
66 investigate the effect of spatial variability of shear strength parameters on runout motion.
67 Therefore, analyzing runout distance of the granular flow in spatially varying soils is still an open
68 question.

69 In recent decades, many probabilistic studies have been conducted as the complementation for
70 deterministic analysis in geotechnical engineering. Spatial variability of soil properties is
71 commonly considered as weakly stationary random fields (Fenton and Griffiths, 2003; Griffiths
72 and Fenton, 2004; Jiang et al., 2014), which is based on random field theory (Vanmarcke, 1977;
73 Nezhad, 2010, Nezhad et al., 2011). In the previous studies, the spatially varying shear strength is
74 usually modeled as a random variable in a structural correlation computational domain (Liu, 2018;
75 Zhang et al., 2018; Gironacci et al., 2018; Nezhad et al., 2018), and the stability/reliability of geo-
76 structures (e.g., foundation or slope) and corresponding probability of failure is evaluated by limit
77 equilibrium method (LEM), finite element method (FEM), or finite difference method (FDM).
78 Among these studies, it can also be noticed that they have been mainly focused on failure
79 probability or pre-failure phase and do not consider the effect of spatial variability on large
80 deformation problems or moving behaviors at post-failure phase. Consequently, post-failure
81 analysis of heterogeneous granular flows is predominantly overlooked in previous works, hence
82 its resulting consequences from the extensive runout of deposits under the effect of inherent spatial

83 variability were also largely ignored. Part of the reason is that large deformation and strain
84 alternation in the computation domain at post-failure phase cannot be easily simulated and
85 analyzed by LEM and FEM methods (e.g., due to mesh dependency, mesh distortion or twisting
86 problems). On the other hand, the lack of such research is partly because of the difficulty in
87 implementing random field information into the modeling framework in an efficient way.

88 In this paper, a generalized interpolation MPM (GIMP) based stochastic numerical modeling
89 framework, termed SGIMP, is employed for simulating granular column collapse in heterogeneous
90 sands with the aim to investigate the spatial variability of shear strength with different
91 autocorrelation functions (ACFs) on the runout distance. The method utilizes both advantages of
92 GIMP and random field theory. According to Crosta et al. (2009), Mohr-Coulomb constitutive
93 model is suitable for capturing the dynamics of collapse in non-cohesive deposits, therefore the
94 whole failure process is modeled by the SGIMP using this constitutive model. Given the large
95 influence of internal friction angle on post-failure behavior (Zhang and Xiao, 2019), it is selected
96 as the random variable and introduced by random field principle. A homogeneous sand collapse
97 and a heterogeneous sand collapse are studied to demonstrate the validity of the method and
98 explore the effects of ACFs and coefficient of variations (COVs) for the internal friction angle
99 parameter. The results of this study can provide a new methodology and insight towards the
100 enforcement of risk assessments for real landslides and other geomaterial flows.

101 **2. Stochastic generalized interpolation material point method**

102 **2.1 Brief review of MPM**

103 MPM was originally developed based on the strengths of particle-in-cell scheme (Sulsky et al.,
104 1994) and FEM. It has been proven as a promising particle-based mesh free method in geotechnical

105 engineering for simulating large strain boundary value problems. The method has been applied to
106 simulate granular flows, slope failures, landslides, embankment collapse and other geological and
107 geotechnical problems (e.g., Andersen and Andersen, 2010; Llano-Serna et al., 2016; Li et al.,
108 2018; Yerro et al., 2019). The essential idea in MPM is to take the advantages of both Lagrangian
109 and Eulerian methods. A cluster of material points (Lagrangian points) is considered representing
110 the continuous material and is allowed to freely move, carrying density, strain, stress, and all state
111 variables of the continuous body; and a Eulerian background mesh is adopted for solving the
112 governing equations of motion and determining incremental velocities, instead of carrying
113 permanent information. In the convection phase, the updated information of grid nodes is mapped
114 back to the material points, and subsequently the grid is regularly reset to the initial configuration
115 and the deformation of the domain is tracked by the motion of the material points. As shown in a
116 computational cycle (Fig. 1), the material points carrying information and background mesh are
117 used to solve motion equations, update the material points, and refresh.

118 In a material domain Ω , it yields the mass and momentum conservation as follows:

119
$$\frac{d\rho}{dt} + \rho \nabla \mathbf{v} = 0 \quad (1)$$

120
$$\rho \frac{d\mathbf{v}}{dt} = \nabla \sigma + \rho \mathbf{b} \quad (2)$$

121 where, ρ is the mass density, \mathbf{v} is the velocity of material, σ is the *Cauchy* stress tensor, \mathbf{b} is
122 the body force, and ∇ is the gradient operator.

123

124

125

Fig. 1 The basic computational cycle in material point method

126 **2.2 Generalized interpolation material point method**

127 The original MPM has grid-crossing instability, which is caused by the discontinuous gradient of
128 shape functions (Bardenhagen et. al., 2002). A sudden change of the stress can be found when a
129 material point crosses to a new cell. This error can be reduced by using GIMP method to introduce
130 GIMP grid shape function and particle characteristic function (Bardenhagen and Kober, 2004).
131 This paper uses GIMP as implemented in the open-source code named MPM3D, from the
132 Computational Dynamics Laboratory, School of Aerospace, Tsinghua University (Zhang et al.,
133 2016). The main computational cycle of GIMP is summarized in the following four steps:

134 1. Firstly, state variables of material points (e.g., mass, momenta, etc.) are interpolated to grid
 135 nodes on the mesh, the mass of a node i and nodal momentum is expressed as:

$$136 \quad m_i = \sum_{p=1}^n S_{ip} m_p \quad (3)$$

$$137 \quad p_i = \sum_{p=1}^n S_{ip} m_p v_p \quad (4)$$

138 where S_{ip} is the computational grid shape function of node i for particle p in GIMP, m_p is
 139 the mass, v_p is the velocity.

140 2. Then the nodal internal force f_i^{int} and external force f_i^{ext} at the node i are expressed as:

$$141 \quad f_i^{int} = - \sum_p \nabla S_{ip} \sigma_p V_p \quad (5)$$

$$142 \quad f_i^{ext} = \sum_p S_{ip} b_p m_p \quad (6)$$

143 where ∇S_{ip} is the gradient of the computational grid shape function over the particle p , σ_p is
 144 the *Cauchy* stress at the particle p , V_p is the volume of the particle, b_p is the corresponding body
 145 force. Based on the forces, the nodal velocities can be updated from:

$$146 \quad v_i^{n+1} = v_i^n + \frac{f_i^{int} + f_i^{ext}}{m_i} \Delta t \quad (7)$$

147 3. The velocity of the particle p can be computed from the updated nodal velocity:

148
$$v_p^{n+1} = v_p^n + \sum_i S_{ip} \frac{f_i^{int} + f_i^{ext}}{m_i} \Delta t \quad (8)$$

149 4. The position of the particle is then updated:

150
$$x_p^{n+1} = x_p^n + \sum_i S_{ip} v_i^{n+1} \Delta t \quad (9)$$

151 Finally, the background mesh is discarded and refreshed to undistorted configuration. Note that
 152 the above computational cycle can be repeated for each incremental step Δt . The used GIMP code
 153 is modified from the openly available MPM3D code (Zhang et al., 2016), which has been
 154 previously exercised by other researchers (e.g., Li et al. 2018).

155 2.3 Random field generation

156 Inherent spatial variability of soil is commonly represented by a numerically generated random
 157 field, which is based on first and second moments of variables and spatial correlation structure
 158 function. To generate a random field of a domain Ω , assume the domain is discretized into n
 159 elements with the centroid coordinates (x_i, y_i) , the autocorrelation matrix $\mathbf{C}_{n \times n}$ defining spatial
 160 structure of the domain can be expressed by:

161
$$\mathbf{C}_{n \times n} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \rho(\tau_{x_{12}}, \tau_{y_{12}}) & \dots & \rho(\tau_{x_{1n}}, \tau_{y_{1n}}) \\ \rho(\tau_{x_{21}}, \tau_{y_{21}}) & 1 & \dots & \rho(\tau_{x_{2n}}, \tau_{y_{2n}}) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \rho(\tau_{x_{n1}}, \tau_{y_{n1}}) & \rho(\tau_{x_{n2}}, \tau_{y_{n2}}) & \dots & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

162 where, n represents the number of random field elements, $\rho(x_{ij}, y_{ij})$ is the autocorrelation
 163 coefficient of quantities between two spatial locations, τ is the absolute distances between the

164 centroid coordinates of the i th element and j th element in horizontal and vertical directions,
 165 respectively.

166 Generally, the correlation of any two variables at different locations is usually characterized by an
 167 ACF in a random field. As reported in the literature, DeGroot and Baecher (1993) adopted the
 168 maximum likelihood method to estimate the corresponding ACF of soil shear strength, Phoon and
 169 Ching (2014) tried to estimate the ACF by using moments method. However, determination of an
 170 appropriate ACF for soil properties is particularly difficult in practice because of limited site
 171 investigation, which requires extensive effort to obtain large quantities of geo-statistical data.
 172 Therefore, theoretical ACFs as alternatives are commonly used to characterize the spatial
 173 variability of soil properties (e.g., Phoon et al., 2003; Li et al., 2015; Liu, 2018). Based on the
 174 findings of previous studies carried out in the probabilistic analysis field, the five most commonly
 175 used theoretical ACFs for geo-statistical analysis can be pointed as; single exponential (SNX),
 176 widely used model to simulate inherent spatial variability of shear strength parameters (Griffiths
 177 and Fenton, 2004; Li et al., 2015), squared exponential (SQX), also named as Gaussian
 178 autocorrelation (Masoudian et al., 2019), cosine exponential (CSX) (Cafaro and Cherubini, 2002;
 179 Liu et al., 2017), second-order Markov (SMK) (Liu et al., 2017; Ching et al., 2019), and Binary
 180 noise (BIN) (Liu et al., 2017; Huang et al., 2018). Table 1 summarizes these five theoretical ACFs.

181 **Table 1.** Common ACFs for geostatistical analysis

Type	ACF in 1-D	Scale of fluctuation	ACF in 2-D
SNX	$\rho(\tau) = \exp(-a\tau)$	$\delta = 2/a$	$\rho(\tau_x, \tau_y) = \exp\left[-2\left(\frac{\tau_x}{\delta_h} + \frac{\tau_y}{\delta_v}\right)\right]$
SQX	$\rho(\tau) = \exp\left[-(b\tau)^2\right]$	$\delta = \sqrt{\pi}b$	$\rho(\tau_x, \tau_y) = \exp\left[-\pi\left(\frac{\tau_x^2}{\delta_h^2} + \frac{\tau_y^2}{\delta_v^2}\right)\right]$

SMK	$\rho(\tau) = \exp(-c\tau)(1 + c\tau)$	$\delta = 4/c$	$\rho(\tau_x, \tau_y) = \exp\left[-4\left(\frac{\tau_x}{\delta_h} + \frac{\tau_y}{\delta_v}\right)\right] \left(1 + \frac{4\tau_x}{\delta_h}\right) \left(1 + \frac{4\tau_y}{\delta_v}\right)$
CSK	$\rho(\tau) = \exp(-d\tau)\cos(d\tau)$	$\delta = 1/d$	$\rho(\tau_x, \tau_y) = \exp\left[-\left(\frac{\tau_x}{\delta_h} + \frac{\tau_y}{\delta_v}\right)\right] \cos\left(\frac{\tau_x}{\delta_h}\right) \cos\left(\frac{\tau_y}{\delta_v}\right)$
BIN	$\rho(\tau) = \begin{cases} 1 - e\tau & \text{for } \tau \leq 1/e \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$	$\delta = 1/e$	$\rho(\tau_x, \tau_y) = \begin{cases} \left(1 - \frac{\tau_x}{\delta_h}\right) \left(1 - \frac{\tau_y}{\delta_v}\right) & \text{for } \tau_x \leq \delta_h \text{ and } \tau_y \leq \delta_v \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$

182 *The a, b, c, d, e are the scale of fluctuation parameters of the ACF model; the lags $\tau_x = |x_i - x_j|$ and
 183 $\tau_y = |y_i - y_j|$ are the absolute distances between two spatial locations in horizontal and vertical directions,
 184 respectively; δ_h and δ_v are the scale of fluctuation in horizontal and vertical directions, respectively .
 185

186 For distinguishing the differences among the ACFs, the 2-D line graph and the 3-D surfaces of the
 187 ACFs are plotted in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3, respectively. It can be found that with the increasing of
 188 normalized absolute distance $|\tau|/\delta$, the corresponding autocorrelation coefficients associated with
 189 ACFs are very different. Meanwhile, significant differences can be observed among these surfaces
 190 of the ACFs, where $\rho(\tau_x, \tau_y)$ is the dependent variable, and τ_x and τ_y are the corresponding
 191 independent variables in horizontal and vertical directions, respectively. As Fig. 3 shows, among
 192 the surfaces, SNX decreases sharply with the increasing of τ_x and τ_y . The surfaces of SNX, CSX,
 193 and BIN ACFs exhibit a sharp corner near the origin and four edges, which are not differentiable.
 194 While the surfaces of SMK and SQX ACFs are very smooth and isotropic, which means the ACFs
 195 are differentiable at the origin. These five ACFs are used in this work to feature the spatial
 196 variability structure of shear strength in the computation domain and are utilized to investigate
 197 how the outputs change with various ACF conditions.

198

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Fig. 2 Common ACFs for geostatistical analysis (normalized to unit scale of fluctuation)

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(a) SNX

(b) SQX

(c) SMK

(d) CSX

(e) BIN

Fig. 3 3-D surfaces of the ACFs for geo-statistical analysis

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207 2.3.1. Cholesky Matrix Decomposition Method

208 The Cholesky matrix decomposition (CMD) method (Li et al., 2015; Liu, 2018; Masoudian et al.,
 209 2019) is adopted in this paper to generate random fields. Karhunen-Loéve expansion method can
 210 also be used for the same purpose; however, its application can result in a complex process as the
 211 eigenvalue of Fredholm integral equation could not be analytically readily solved (Zhu et al.,
 212 2017). CDM is computationally very efficient and easily implementable, it is also very robustly
 213 coping with multivariate random fields (Phoon et al., 2003; Phoon and Ching, 2014; Li et al.,
 214 2015). More details about generating random fields by using CMD can be found in Zhu et al.
 215 (2017). By using CMD, the autocorrelation matrix $\mathbf{C}_{n \times n}$ can be decomposed as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{C}_{n \times n} &= \mathbf{L} \cdot \mathbf{L}^T \\
 &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & \dots \\ \rho & \sqrt{1-\rho^2} & \dots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \rho & \dots \\ 0 & \sqrt{1-\rho^2} & \dots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots \end{bmatrix}
 \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

217 where, \mathbf{L} is the lower triangular matrix with dimension of $n \times n$. An anisotropic standard
 218 Gaussian random field \mathbf{X}^G can be derived as follows:

$$\mathbf{X}^G(x, y) = \mathbf{L} \cdot \xi_i \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, N) \tag{12}$$

220 where i is the number of standard Gaussian random field, ξ_i is a sample matrix obtained by
 221 arranging the vector of n independent standard normal random variables as m vectors with
 222 dimension of n . Subsequently, the standard Gaussian random field \mathbf{X}^G is used to generate the Non-
 223 Gaussian random field \mathbf{X}^{NG} of desired values by isoprobabilistic transformation method (Li et al.,
 224 2015) as:

225
$$\mathbf{X}^{NG}(x, y) = F^{-1}\Phi[\mathbf{X}^G(x, y)] \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, N) \quad (13)$$

226 where the $F^{-1}(\bullet)$ is the inverse function of its corresponding marginal cumulative
227 distribution of the desired variable given its mean μ , standard deviation σ , and probability
228 distribution; $\Phi(\bullet)$ is the standard Gaussian cumulative distribution function. The $\Phi(\bullet)$ can
229 rearrange the standard Gaussian random field \mathbf{X}^G into the uniform distribution $\mathbf{U} = \Phi[\mathbf{X}^G(x, y)]$
230 within (0,1). Thereafter, non-Gaussian random field \mathbf{X}^{NG} can be generated by Eq. (13), the
231 procedure can be repeated N times to obtain N realisations of the random field.

232 **2.4. Implementation and workflow of the framework**

233 Fig. 4 outlines the basics of the SGIMP framework employed in this work, which consists of three
234 important steps:

235 **Step 1.** In the pre-process phase, the random variable \mathbf{X} is set up based on the point statistics (mean
236 μ_X , variance σ_X , and assumed distribution type, e.g., normal distribution), and the modules
237 are initialized.

238 **Step 2.** In the SGIMP, Monte-Carlo simulation (MCS) is implemented for the stochastic modeling.
239 After setting the total realization number N , the current simulation starts from $i = 1$. Based
240 on a set of random seed numbers, \mathbf{s} , the coordinates (x, y) of model geometry including
241 the boundary conditions Γ , spatial structure defined by ACFs, and spatial statistics (scale
242 of fluctuation δ), a set of isotropic Gaussian random fields $\mathbf{X}^G(x, y)$ can be generated.
243 Then, it is transformed into the non-Gaussian random field $\mathbf{X}^{NG}(x, y)$ in the physical space
244 by Eq. (13). It can be observed that all random fields may look similar in pattern; however,

245 they differ with respect to the spatial distribution of mechanically strong and weak zones
246 that will lead to different output responses. The i -th set of spatially correlated soil property
247 values $X^{NG}(x, y)$ is then transmitted to the mechanical module, which has been developed
248 to perform the large deformation analysis. Meanwhile, a single set of deterministic model
249 parameters \mathbf{D} (e.g., density ρ , Young's modulus E , Poisson's ratio ν) is transmitted to the
250 mechanical module. After both deterministic model parameters and stochastic model
251 parameters are prepared, the mechanical module starts to run the modeling and receives
252 back a discrete response measure, runout distance $y = S_x$. This communication continues
253 for N times realizations and until convergence of the first and second moments of the
254 model outputs occurs. Here, it is assumed that the convergence occurs when the differences
255 in the calculated values for mean and variance obtained in consequent MC iterations
256 become less than 10^{-3} .

257 In the mechanical module, the most significant work about transmission of random fields to the
258 mechanical module are highlighted. After running a MATLAB code of CMD method, the obtained
259 i -th non-Gaussian random field $X^{NG}(x, y)$ of computation domain Ω holding the shear strength
260 parameters of the geomaterial (in here the internal friction angle φ of sand) are mapped onto each
261 material point in the GIMP instead of grid nodes as shown in Fig. 5. The transmission process is
262 based on spatial relationship between material point and random field element (e.g., a position-to-
263 position mapping process), which is similar with the RFEM sharing the same value on elements
264 of random fields and FEM mesh (Huang and Griffiths, 2015).

265 Therefore, a deterministic GIMP calculation is performed after carrying a set of random
266 mechanical property values on the material points. Consequently, stochastic modeling is conducted

267 and the output runout distance S_x is determined for each realization, i.e., $S_x = \{S_{x_1}, S_{x_2}, \dots, S_{x_n}\}^T$.

268 It should be noted that each simulation index, i , would be updated and checked; if $i \leq N$ the MCS

269 is aborted, otherwise it is continued.

270 **Step 3.** In the post-processing phase, all calculated data are processed to compute the mean values,

271 variances, and PDFs, and they will be compared with the corresponding homogeneous

272 model outputs to investigate the effect of spatial variability on the runout distances. This

273 framework can be easily extended to account for the uncertainty in other shear strength

274 parameters of the deposit, such as undrained shear strength S_u , and any geometry.

275 Furthermore, the outcomes can be used to assess and mitigate the potential damages

276 incurred by large deformations during geo-disasters.

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Fig. 4 Flowchart illustrating the employed SGIMP model framework

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Fig. 5 Schematics of the mapping process of a random field in SGIMP

281 **3. Stochastic analysis of sand column collapse**

282 **3.1. Numerical model setup**

283 3.1.1. Deterministic model parameters

284 The numerical model is setup as a plane strain problem. Fig. 6 shows the initial geometry of the
285 sand column model with 5.0×5.0 m, and the distance from the right side of the sand column to
286 the right-side boundary is 15.0 m for allowing enough runout distance for the sand flow. The
287 computation domain is discretized into 6400 material points with a radius of 0.0625 m (0.625 dm)
288 and covered by a total of 10170 background computational grids with side length of 0.125 mm
289 (1.25 dm). The background computational mesh is made up of 4-noded quadrilateral elements,
290 where each grid contains 4 (2×2) material points inside. The bottom boundary $y = 0$ is fully
291 fixed in the x , y , z directions. While roller boundary conditions are set for allowing vertical
292 displacements at both lateral boundaries ($x = 0$ and $x = 20$ m). On the boundaries of $z = 0$ m and
293 $z = 0.0625$ m, the grid nodes are fixed in the z -direction. Lube et al. (2004) suggested that the
294 roughness of the base surface on which the sand spreads has a negligible effect on the runout
295 distance. This can be explained by the fact that the majority of the actual flow generally occurs
296 over the base of the deposit. Therefore, rough contact, inherent in the MPM, was used in the
297 analysis. The time increment is 2.0×10^{-2} s and total time for the calculation is 5 s when deposits
298 become stable according to kinetic energy and unbalanced forces of the system (Kafaji 2013).

299 A Mohr-Coulomb model is used to describe the sand behavior, the material properties are
300 summarized in Table 2. To realistically model the post-failure behavior of the sand collapse, a
301 numerical damping is introduced for approximating the energy loss of grains on movement, which
302 is mainly influenced by the effect of friction between particles (Sołowski and Sloan, 2015).

303 Without such damping factor, the spreads of sand particles can be too far (Sołowski and Sloan,
 304 2013). The numerical damping is applied using:

$$305 \quad a_I = a_I - c_d v_I \quad (14)$$

306 where a_I is the acceleration of the nodes on the background grids, v_I is the velocity of nodes on
 307 the background grids and c_d is the damping coefficient. In the model, the value of damping
 308 coefficient has been selected as 2.

309 **Table 2.** Material properties of the sand

Parameters	unit	Values
Bulk density, ρ	kg/m ³	1450
Young's modulus, E	kPa	2600
Poisson's ratio, ν		0.31
Internal friction angle, ϕ	°	35

310

311

312 **Fig. 6** Geometry and boundary conditions of the model

313 3.1.2. Stochastic model parameters

314 Sand is a natural geomaterial with heterogeneities subject to long-term geological processes. Since
 315 Lumb (1966, 1970) investigated the natural variability of internal friction angle of sand, many
 316 researchers started to build random variable model for sand. It is admitted that even small-scale
 317 heterogeneities of internal friction angle φ have strong influence on macroscopic behavior, such
 318 as internal structure deformation and flow distances (Hung, 1995). Therefore, this soil strength
 319 parameter is selected as the random variable for the analysis. Different plausible ranges of
 320 variations for both $\tan\varphi$ and φ of sand, according to the literature, are summarized in Table 3.

321 **Table 3.** General summary of the ranges of the COV reported in the literature for friction angle
 322 of sand

Values of COV	PDF	Reference
$COV_{\tan\varphi} = 0.058$	-	Lumb (1966)
$COV_{\varphi} = 0.053$	Log-normal distribution	Schultze (1972)
$COV_{\tan\varphi} = 0.073$		
$0.05 \leq COV_{\tan\varphi} \leq 0.14$	-	Schultze (1975)
$0.037 \leq COV_{\varphi} \leq 0.093$	Normal distribution	Wolff et al. (1996)
$0.05 \leq COV_{\varphi} \leq 0.11$	-	Phoon and Kulhawy (1996)
$0.05 \leq COV_{\tan\varphi} \leq 0.14$	-	
$0.02 \leq COV_{\varphi} \leq 0.05$	Normal distribution	Lacasse and Nadim (1997)
$COV_{\varphi} = 0.059$		
$0.05 \leq COV_{\tan\varphi} \leq 0.15$	-	Cherubini (2000)
$0.054 \leq COV_{\tan\varphi} \leq 0.167$	-	Wang et al. (2010)

323
 324 According to the summary, in this work, the internal friction angles are described by a normal
 325 distribution and the statistical characteristics of sand parameters are displayed in Table 4. The

326 mean value is $\mu_\varphi=35^\circ$ and values of coefficient of variation, COV_φ , equal to 0.05, 0.10, and 0.15,
 327 are used to study the effect of degree of heterogeneity on the macroscopic response. Only isotropic
 328 random fields with $\delta_h = \delta_v = 0.2\text{ m}$ are used in this study (usually 0.13 m to 0.71 m), which is
 329 based on the CPT cone resistance data reported in the literature (Campanella et al., 1987; Nie et
 330 al., 2015).

331 **Table 4.** Statistical parameters of the internal friction angle φ of sand

Parameters	unit	Values	Distribution
Mean, μ_φ	°	35	Normal distribution
COV_φ	-	0.05, 0.10, 0.15	
Horizontal fluctuation, δ_h	m	0.2	
Vertical fluctuation, δ_v	m	0.2	

332

333 4. Numerical modeling

334 4.1. Homogeneous sand collapse modeling

335 By conducting the homogeneous sand collapse modeling with constant parameters in Table 2, the
 336 runout distance S_x of sand collapse at critical times are presented in Fig. 7. For better visualization
 337 of the modeling, the unit is set as decimeter (dm). When $t=1.4\text{ s}$, the runout distance starts
 338 increasing rapidly, and a large deformation can be observed. When $t=4.2\text{ s}$, the sand collapse is
 339 stable, and its final runout distance reaches 60.03 dm.

340

341

(a) $t = 1.4$ s

(b) $t = 1.8$ s

342

343

(c) $t = 2.6$ s

(d) $t = 4.2$ s

344 **Fig. 7** Homogeneous sand collapse process represented by horizontal runout distance at different
345 times

346 4.2. Heterogeneous sand collapse modeling

347 From this section on, a stochastic modeling of sand collapse considering the effect of soil
348 heterogeneity is conducted, in which the five previously introduced ACFs and three different
349 values of COV_{φ} are used to specify the most influential heterogeneous characteristics on the
350 mechanical responses. In these simulations, the baseline case is defined when the COV_{φ} is taken
351 as 0.05, and the horizontal and vertical scale of fluctuations are taken as $\delta_h = \delta_v = 0.2$ m.

352 Fig. 8 presents the typical samples of random fields of φ with the baseline case parameters
353 associated with the SNX, SQX, SMK, CSX, and BIN ACFs. In these figures, the red regions denote
354 larger φ values representing the mechanically strong zones, while the blue regions represent
355 relatively smaller φ values specifying the mechanically weaker zones in the sand column. All
356 typical samples of random fields show that heterogeneity causes a random distribution of local
357 weakness (low values of φ) in the domains. These weak zones will introduce different final output
358 responses, which cannot be predicted by homogeneous modeling. It can also be observed that the
359 generated random samples associated with SQX and SMK ACFs present relatively smoother

360 variations among sand friction angle values, hence they provide more realistic representation of
 361 the spatially correlated soil strength characteristic (Li et al., 2015). While the SNX, CSX, and BIN
 362 ACFs result in generating random samples with higher degrees of fluctuation, where the random
 363 values vary quite roughly (as shown in Fig. 8).

364

365

(a) SNX

(b) SQX

366

367

(c) SMK

(d) CSX

368

369

(e) BIN

370 **Fig. 8** Typical samples of random fields associated with the ACFs of $COV_{\varphi} = 0.05$, $\delta_h = \delta_v =$
 371 0.2 m, red and blue regions depict mechanically “strong” and “weak” sand, respectively.

372

373 Fig. 9 shows the collapse status of the heterogeneous sand at final state, predicted by using different
374 ACFs in the SGIMP simulations. With different ACFs, the frontal deposits spread over a range,
375 from about 110 dm to over 120 dm, that demonstrates the impact of considering sand heterogeneity
376 on the modeling results.

377 To comprehensively analyze the impact of the key mechanical features on the runout distance, the
378 stochastic response of the runout distance S_x is computed using MCS with different ACFs and
379 $COV\phi$ values. The number of samples is crucial for the statistical accuracy. Large numbers would
380 lead to more accurate estimations with lower errors, but they require dramatic computational time.
381 Therefore, an appropriate MCS number is determined by compromising between the efficiency
382 and accuracy. In this work, both the mean values and standard deviations of the S_x for the five
383 ACFs with the baseline cases are plotted as functions of the number of MCS. It demonstrates that
384 after about 700 simulations the statistical convergence is achieved (Fig. 10). Therefore, one
385 thousand realizations are performed for each case to confirm stable statistical results and
386 computational efficiency. Each realization takes about 8 ~ 10 minutes when using a PC with an
387 Intel Core i7-6700 3.40 GHz processor with 8 cores and 16 GB memory.

388

389

(a) SNX

(b) SQX

390

391

(c) SMK

(d) CSX

392

393

(e) BIN

394

Fig. 9 Final configuration of the heterogeneous sand collapse ($COV_{\varphi} = 0.05$)

(a) Means vs. number of the statistical samples.

(b) Standard deviation vs. number of the statistical samples.

395 **Fig. 10** Variations of the mean and standard deviation of the S_x with the number of MCS samples
396 based on the baseline case.

397 4.2.1. Effect of ACFs on runout distance

398 In the previous section, the effects of different ACFs on the runout distance of heterogeneous sand
399 collapse were investigated by the SGIMP analysis in which 1000 samples of friction angle random
400 field were generated and evaluated to obtain an accurate estimation of each case. In order to
401 identify the distribution of the computed runout distance for each case, four different types of
402 statistical distributions including normal distribution, lognormal distribution, Gumbel and Weibull
403 distributions are examined. A goodness-of-fit test method is applied to identify the best-fit
404 marginal distribution underlying the computed data. In this work, both the Akaike information
405 criterion (AIC) (Akaike, 1974) and Bayesian information criterion (BIC) (Schwarz, 1978) are
406 adopted to identify the best-fit distributions, they are defined as

$$407 \quad \text{AIC} = -2 \sum_{i=1}^N \ln f[(x_i; p, q)] + 2k_1 \quad (15)$$

$$408 \quad \text{BIC} = -2 \sum_{i=1}^N \ln f[(x_i; p, q)] + k_1 \ln N \quad (16)$$

409 where x_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, N$) is the output S_x from the SGIMP; N is the number of samples;
410 $f(x_i; p, q)$ is the PDF of alternative marginal distribution function, p and q are the parameters of
411 distribution; k_1 is the number of distribution parameters in the alternative marginal distribution.
412 For the above-mentioned marginal distribution function, k_1 is considered to be equal to 2 (Phoon
413 and Ching, 2014; Zhang et. al., 2018).

414 Table 5 shows the AIC and BIC values associated with the four distributions for various ACF
 415 conditions. Note that the distribution associated with the smallest AIC and BIC values is identified
 416 to be the best-fit marginal distribution to the output data (Zhang et. al., 2018). It is found that both
 417 the AIC and BIC values indicate the Gumbel distribution is the best-fit distribution for the output
 418 runout distance of all cases.

419 **Table 5.** AIC and BIC values for the candidate distributions

ACF	Normal [AIC, BIC]	Lognormal [AIC, BIC]	Gumbel [AIC, BIC]	Weibull [AIC, BIC]
SNX	702.86, 708.07	693.00, 698.21	676.12, 681.33*	738.54, 743.75
SQX	714.45, 719.66	699.41, 704.62	676.15, 681.36*	767.03, 772.24
SMK	677.71, 682.92	665.38, 670.59	642.25, 647.46*	741.22, 746.43
CSX	688.59, 693.80	675.25, 680.46	652.28, 657.49*	751.64, 756.85
BIN	722.87, 728.08	708.45, 713.66	687.49, 692.70*	768.87, 774.08

420 *Denotes the minimum AIC and BIC values, which correspond to the best-fit distributions.

421 The PDF of the Gumbel distribution is expressed as (Phoon and Ching, 2014):

$$422 \quad f(x; p, q) = \frac{q \exp\{-q(x-p) - \exp[-q(x-p)]\}}{\{1 - \exp[-\exp(pq)]\}} \quad (17)$$

$$423 \quad \mu = p + 0.5772/q \quad (18)$$

$$424 \quad \sigma^2 = \pi^2/(6q^2) \quad (19)$$

425 where p and q are the parameters of distribution, μ is the mean value, and σ is the standard
 426 deviation. In this work, maximum likelihood method is adopted to estimate the corresponding
 427 parameters of the Gumbel distribution. The mean and deviation of stochastic data can be obtained
 428 by equations (17-19).

429 Fig. 11 shows the distributions and mean values of runout distance S_x of each heterogeneous sand
430 collapse case associated with different ACFs. It should be noted that the probabilistic post-failure
431 behavior analysis is different from the pre-failure analysis such as stability analysis or reliability
432 analysis. The effect of ACFs on runout distance shows different features compared with other
433 works (e.g., stability or reliability analysis of slopes (Li et al. 2015; Ching and Phoon 2019)).
434 Because of the diverse spatial distribution of friction angle generated by different ACFs, each
435 output runout distance is different. The runout distances predicted by the heterogeneous models
436 range from 57 dm to 89 dm. By comparing the mean values, the results of SNX with a value of
437 63.47 dm are larger than those obtained by the other ACFs. While the results of SQX and SMK
438 are very close to each other with 62.54 dm and 62.65 dm, respectively. The results achieved by
439 CSX and BIN are relatively smaller than the other cases, with 62.35 dm and 62.37 dm,
440 respectively. The relative difference in mean value of the runout distance associated with these
441 ACFs can be explained by their function graphs and expressions. According to Fig. 3, a sharp
442 decrease can be observed in the SNX surface, which suggests that the random internal friction
443 angle based on SNX spatially fluctuates significantly, thus predicting larger values for the runout
444 distance. As for other ACFs, the surfaces are relatively smooth, presenting more realistic variations
445 than those of the SNX ACF, which result in more reliable predictions. This is consistent with the
446 previous findings of Uzielli et al. (2005) that SMK and CSX are suitable for characterizing the
447 spatial correlation of shear strength of sands.

448 In Fig. 12, it can be observed that the effect of ACFs on runout motion of sand collapse are slightly
449 different, in which SNX shows the largest impact on post-failure behavior of flows among the
450 different ACF cases. Additionally, the homogeneous model underestimates the runout distance
451 with only 60.03 dm, which is apparently because the effect of local spatial variation in the friction

452 angle is not considered in the deterministic analysis. A recognizable difference can be noticed in
453 terms of φ of the sand. In addition, between 55% to 68% of the runout distances predicted by the
454 heterogeneous models with all cases exceeding the runout distance obtained by the deterministic
455 model, which means there is a large uncertainty in prediction of the runout distances. Because flow
456 of the granular materials depends on the interparticle frictions (Crosta et al., 2009), the spatial
457 variation of φ would significantly influence the post-failure behavior. Therefore, the
458 homogeneous model cannot reproduce the aspect of the post-failure behavior of the heterogenous
459 sand collapse and as such it cannot predict the real post-failure behavior and the runout distance
460 of the sand collapse.

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461

462

(a) SNX

(b) SQX

463

464

(c) SMK

(d) CSX

465

466

(e) BIN

467

Fig. 11 Histograms, PDF and mean values of S_x with the ACF cases

468

469
470
471
472

Fig. 12 (a) PDFs with the ACFs compared with homogenous results, (b) Mean values and standard deviations of S_x with the ACFs.

473 4.2.2. Effect of COV_ϕ on runout distance

474 To investigate the effect of COV_ϕ on the runout distance of the heterogeneous sand collapse, the
 475 COV_ϕ is increased from 0.05 to 0.15 with constant $\delta_h = \delta_v = 0.2$ m in each ACF case. A total of
 476 5000 simulations have been conducted. According to the statistics, the mean values and standard
 477 deviations of the runout distance in each case (considering different COV_ϕ values) are plotted in
 478 Fig. 13, and compared with the runout distances predicted by the deterministic analysis.

479

480

(a) SNX

(b) SQX

481

482

(c) SMK

(d) CSX

483

484

(e) BIN

(f) Comparison with different cases

485 **Fig. 13** Mean values and standard deviations of the runout distances considering different COV_{φ}

486 All results show that the mean values of the runout distance increase with increasing COV_{φ} , and

487 all the mean values are larger than the value obtained from the homogeneous model. Additionally,

488 the number of the extreme values of the runout distance increases with the COV_{φ} increase. For a

489 small COV_{φ} , the varying range of φ is correspondingly narrowed. Thereby, the distribution of the

490 runout distances will be narrower. On the other hand, a large COV_{φ} causes a wide range of values
491 for φ , subsequently resulting in a wider distribution of the runout distance. Therefore, the standard
492 deviations of the runout distance become large with the increase in COV_{φ} value.

493 Fig. 14 shows the exceedance probability of the predicted runout distances (S_x) by all
494 heterogeneous cases that larger runout distance is obtained compared to that of the deterministic
495 analysis. It shows that the uncertainty in predicting the S_x is significantly enlarged as COV_{φ}
496 increases. Moreover, it is found that different ACFs have relatively different effects on the S_x
497 outputs when COV_{φ} is increasing, but the overall trends are similar with each other. As for SMK,
498 the result with $COV_{\varphi}=0.05$ illustrates that only 39% of the predicted cases exceed the
499 deterministic value, which indicates that the smallest uncertainty on S_x is when using SMK. While
500 the results with $COV_{\varphi}=0.15$, generating from CSX, demonstrate the largest uncertainty in
501 predicting the runout distance, as 74% of the outputs exceed the deterministic value. All
502 probabilities of the runout distance exceed the value obtained by the homogeneous model,
503 indicating that sand heterogeneity significantly influences on the magnitude of the runout distance
504 and post-failure behavior. It also indicates that potentially longer runout distance can be caused by
505 the increasing of COV_{φ} .

506

507

Fig. 14 Probability of S_x exceeding the deterministically predicted value in each case

508 5. Conclusion

509 A SGIMP framework is proposed for probabilistic analysis of runout distance in sand collapse
510 considering the heterogeneity of soil shear strength. The framework is based on the integration of
511 random fields theory and GIMP into a Monte-Carlo simulation basis. Heterogeneity and large
512 deformation are both considered in this method, and the capability of the SGIMP framework to
513 estimate the runout distance of heterogeneous sand collapse has been explored, through which the
514 effects of different ACFs and COV on the runout distance have also been investigated. The main
515 findings of the study are summarized in the following:

- 516 1. The proposed SGIMP framework can be used to generate reasonable random fields for
517 stochastic large-deformation failure analysis, and it provides a practical tool for solving large
518 deformation problems in deposits with prominent heterogeneity.

519 2. Using the proposed framework, a heterogeneous sand collapse is simulated with both
520 homogeneous and heterogeneous conditions. The results show that the homogeneous model
521 may underestimate the runout distance while the stochastic-based analysis provides more
522 realistic results. Due to the differences of adopted ACFs, the runout distance outputs
523 associated with different ACFs are dissimilar. Among the five ACFs, it is shown that SNX
524 results in the largest possible post-failure material flow with apparent overestimation of
525 runout distances. As for other ACFs, more realistic variations of soil strength parameter are
526 obtained which result in more reliable predictions. In particular, SMK and CSX seem to be
527 the most suitable for characterizing the spatial correlation of shear strengths.

528 3. The COV_{φ} affects the runout distance of sand collapse. The uncertainty of runout distance
529 increases with COV_{φ} increasing, accordingly the distribution of the runout distance also
530 increases, which indicates that the deviations of the runout distance become larger.

531 4. According to the proportion of the runout distance that exceeds the deterministic value in
532 each case, the results imply that a deterministic analysis would significantly underestimate
533 the potential risk caused by the large runout distance induced by heterogeneous sand collapse.

534 As has been clarified, the main focus of this paper was to study the implications of using different
535 ACFs on stochastic analysis of post-failure runouts due to sand collapse within a SGIMP
536 framework. However, it should be mentioned that, within this framework, there are other factors
537 or considerations worth investigating in future works, for example the natural non-stationary
538 characteristics of soil properties (e.g., Ma et al. 2022) or employing more advanced material
539 models (e.g., Wang et al. 2020).

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